

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

Google Scholar

YEAR: 2024

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

**A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

This is certified that the Paper Title “A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE PERSONALITY OF GIRL STUDENTS STUDYING IN GIRLS’ AND CO-EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS” authored by “Dr. Rajinder Kaur Gill” has been published in the Volume-(2) Issue-(3) Oct-Dec 2025, ADEJ with **PIF:1.024(I2OR)** & **3.125(IIFS)** with *plagiarism free through rigorous blind peer review process in term of originality and quality of work by review committee of ADEJ.*

www.educarepublication.com

adeduxian@gmail.com

copyright@adeduxianpublication

Mrs. JYOTISHA PANDEY
Managing Director
AD EDUXIAN PUBLICATION
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India